

A Cross-Sectional Study to Elucidate the Indications for HFNC Therapy in Children of All Ages and Diagnoses, and to Evaluate the Efficacy and Risk Factors for Failure of HFNC Therapy

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Aim: The aims of this study were to elucidate the indications for HFNC therapy in children of all ages and diagnoses, and to evaluate the efficacy and risk factors for failure of HFNC therapy.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was undertaken at Department of Pediatrics, Nalanda Medical College and hospital Patna, Bihar, India and consecutive patients with respiratory distress necessitating admission to PICU, in the age group of 1 month to 16 years of age were included.

Results: A total of 200 children were commenced on HFNC therapy. HFNC failure occurred in 20 children at a median (IQR) time of 2 (1.75-24) hours. In univariate regression analysis, respiratory clinical score [Hazard ratio (95% CI) 4.9 (2.1-11.2), P=0.001]; SF ratio [HR (95% CI) 0.94 (0.97-0.99), P=0.012]; and COMFORT score, [HR (95% CI) 1.99 (1.4-2.8), P=0.001] on admission were associated with HFNC failure. In multivariable regression analysis, none of these parameters were associated with increased risk of HFNC failure, respiratory clinical score [HR (95% CI) 2.26 (0.84-7.7), P=0.09], SF ratio, [HR (95% CI) 0.99 (0.97- 1.00), P=0.29] and COMFORT score [HR (95% CI) 1.39 (0.88-2.21), P=0.15].

Conclusion: HFNC is an effective and safe primary mode of respiratory support in children with respiratory distress due to various causes. Children who succeed on HFNC show favourable response within first few hours and response is sustained over the next few days.

Keywords: Comfort Score, Mechanical Ventilation, Non-Invasive Ventilation, SaO₂/FiO₂ Ratio.

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Introduction

Oxygen supply via high-flow nasal cannula (HFNC) is a technique for non-invasive respiratory support, which can be placed, regarding the level of support, between conventional oxygen therapy and

noninvasive ventilation. It has been primarily developed

for premature infants as an alternative to non-invasive positive pressure ventilation (nasal continuous positive airway pressure (nCPAP)) [1-3]. Acute respiratory distress

is the most common cause of pediatric intensive care unit admission. Invasive mechanical ventilation is an established effective supportive therapy for acute respiratory distress. High-flow nasal cannulas (HFNCs) are an increasingly used form of non-invasive respiratory support, and they have shown potential in reducing the need for intubation [4–7]. HFNCs enable the administration of high concentrations of oxygen with adequate relative humidity and temperature, and they have been shown to improve airway resistance and lung compliance, achieve a certain level of continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP), eliminate dead space and decrease respiratory work [8–11]. This helps to prevent mucosal dryness

and increases the tolerance for the patient [7]. A consistent high flow rate leads to a reduced alveolar carbon dioxide concentration and thus reduced hypercapnia [12].

In neonates and infants a flow rate of 2 L/kg/min has been proposed, whereas in children flow rates should get closer to 1 L/kg/min [8,13]. As respiratory support with nCPAP, the HFNC-system provides a positive airway pressure and thus builds up a positive end expiratory Pressure (PEEP), which can be similar, greater or less than those produced by the nCPAP-systems [14-16]. HFNC therapy has been used in infants with respiratory distress syndrome and infants with bronchiolitis, and it has been shown to decrease respiratory distress and intubation rates, increase patient comfort and ease of use compared with facemasks or traditional cannulas, and shorten the length of stay in pediatric intensive care units (ICUs) [17-20]. Furthermore, due to the humidified and heated gas-mixture, children tolerate HFNC better than conventional oxygen supply, because of not having the sense of dry nasal or oral mucosa [10]. The humidified and heated air also improves the mucociliary clearance. Thus, the aims of this study were to elucidate the

indications for HFNC therapy in children of all ages and diagnoses, and to evaluate the efficacy and risk factors for failure of HFNC therapy.

Material & Methods

A cross-sectional study was undertaken at Department of Pediatrics, Nalanda Medical College and hospital Patna, Bihar, India for six months and consecutive patients with respiratory distress necessitating admission to PICU, in the age group of 1 month to 16 years of age were included. Children requiring immediate noninvasive (NIV) or invasive ventilation and those with contraindications to HFNC, altered sensorium (GCS <12), apnea and catecholamine resistant shock were excluded. Acute respiratory distress was defined as hypoxemia (SpO₂ < 94%) and signs of respiratory distress despite standard-flow oxygen therapy. All patients received standard-flow oxygen therapy via a traditional nasal cannula at 1–5 L/min, simple mask at 6–10 L/min or oxygen hood with 35–50% oxygen before they were switched to high flow (16, 17). The signs of respiratory distress included increased breathing rate and heart rate, color changes, grunting, nose flaring, retractions, wheezing, and sweating.

The eligibility criteria for this study were:

1. Age from 1 month to 16 years; and
2. Patients with acute respiratory distress with hypoxia who used HFNC respiratory support for any period of time during their pediatric ICU admission.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Were older than 18 years and younger than 1 month;
2. Had respiratory distress with low-flow oxygen therapy (such as a traditional nasal cannula at 1–5 L/min, simple mask at 6–10 L/min or oxygenhood with 35–50% oxygen) or respiratory

- failure with invasive mechanical ventilation;
- Required respiratory support post extubation and after weaning from continuous positive airway pressure (CPAP) or bilevel positive airway pressure (BIPAP);
 - Had a history of long-term ventilator dependency.

Data Collection

The following information was collected for all patients: (1) demographics and underlying medical history; (2) primary indication and respiratory infection status; (3) clinical parameters of disease severity, including heart rate, breathing rate, SpO₂, venous blood gas from a central venous catheter, including pH and PCO₂, as well as Pediatric Risk of Mortality (PRISM) III score, the initial and lowest level S/F ratio and the ROX index score; (4) variables after HFNC respiratory support, including initial and maximum HFNC parameters

(FiO₂ and flow) and duration of HFNC use; and (5) outcomes. The primary indication was defined according to the discharge summary and treatment modalities used during the ICU stay. The primary outcome was defined as success or failure of HFNC respiratory support, and the second outcome was defined as 1-month mortality, and lengths of pediatric ICU and hospital stay.

Statistical Analysis

The statistical analysis has been performed using IBM SPSS version 22 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, USA) and graphic representation of the results was made with Microsoft Excel 2016 (Microsoft Corporation, USA) and Prism Version 6.0 (GraphPad Software, Lo Jolla, USA).

A p-value less than 0.05 were considered to be statistically significant.

Results

	HFNC responders (n=180)	Non- responders (n=20)	P value
Age			
<6 mo	33 (18.34)	5 (25)	0.01
6-23 mo	60 (33.33)	7 (35)	0.001
2-5 y	70 (38.88)	4 (20)	0.001
6-12 y	15 (8.33)	4 (20)	0.001
13-16 y	2 (1.12)	0	0.001
Diagnosis			
Bronchiolitis	35 (19.44)	1 (5)	0.001
Pneumonia	52 (28.88)	15 (75)	0.001
LRTI with wheezing	15 (8.34)	1 (5)	0.001
Acute severe asthma	15 (8.34)	0	0.001
Congenital heart disease	7 (3.88)	0	0.001
Septic shock	41 (22.77)	3 (15)	0.001
Others	15 (8.34)	0	0.001
FiO ₂ (%)	40 (35-45)	60 (55-70)	0.08
Flow (L/min)	15 (11-20)	16 (13-22)	0.45
PIM2 score (%)	2.7 (1.1-6.4)	5 (4-14.3)	0.01
Mortality	0	3	0.001
Respiratory clinical score			
On admission	10 (9-11)	12 (11-12)	0.001
At 60-90 min	9 (8-10)	12 (11-12)	0.001
At 12-24 h	7 (6-8)	12 (11-12)	0.001

SF ratio			
On admission	316 (262-330)	260 (236-323)	0.03
At 60-90 min	333 (281-346)	245 (217-246)	≤0.001
At 12-24 h	360 (306-374)	245 (196-252)	≤0.001
COMFORT score			
On admission	31 (29-33)	33 (32-35)	≤0.001
At 60-90 min	29 (27-30)	33 (32-35)	≤0.001
At 12-24 h	25 (24-26)	34 (32-35)	≤0.001

A total of 200 children were commenced on HFNC therapy. HFNC failure occurred in 20 children at a median (IQR) time of 2 (1.75-24) hours. In univariate regression analysis, respiratory clinical score [Hazard ratio (95% CI) 4.9 (2.1-11.2), P=0.001]; SF ratio [HR (95% CI) 0.94 (0.97-0.99), P=0.012]; and COMFORT score, [HR (95% CI) 1.99 (1.4-2.8), P=

0.001] on admission were associated with HFNC failure. In multivariable regression analysis, none of these parameters were associated with increased risk of HFNC failure, respiratory clinical score [HR (95% CI) 2.26 (0.84-7.7), P=0.09], SF ratio, [HR (95% CI) 0.99 (0.97- 1.00), P=0.29] and COMFORT score [HR (95% CI) 1.39 (0.88-2.21), P=0.15].

Discussion

Humidified flow nasal cannula (HFNC) delivers heated and humidified gas mixture at a flow greater than patient's inspiratory flow demand and can provide intermediate level of support between low-flow oxygen delivery and noninvasive ventilation (NIV) in critically ill children [12]. Retrospective studies have shown that HFNC is useful for conditions like bronchiolitis, asthma, pneumonia and congenital heart disease [18]. The evidence for its safety or usefulness in children is limited [13].

HFNC was effective in preventing intubation in children with respiratory distress in the present study with low failure rate in patients with various respiratory etiologies. The low failure rate on HFNC could be because was started relatively early and pre-emptively, even in cases of mild to moderate illness. Patients

with shock were also managed successfully on HFNC in this study. The contribution of HFNC in recovery of these patients cannot be quantified since multimodal monitoring and management plays a more important role. However, HFNC helps in decreasing work of breathing in these patients by maintaining functional residual capacity.

HFNC use requires additional treatment modalities before invasive ventilation which can be associated with adverse events and additional costs [19]. It may also be associated with delay in intubation, which however, was not seen in the present study. Our survey displayed the increasing use of HFNC on intensive care units, crossing the border of primary neonatal care and widening the indications. We showed that HFNC is considered for more and more diseases from the pediatric spectrum, like pneumonia, obstructive bronchitis or respiratory support in patients with cystic fibrosis or neuromuscular diseases. This observation matches with the growing number of publications regarding the use of HFNC as oxygen supply for diseases of the pediatric and adolescent spectrum and nowadays even in adults [20,21].

Previous studies regarding HFNC observed that the proximal airway pressure varied strongly depending on flow rates, mouth opening and nasal cannula size in comparison to the size of the nares diameter [21-23]. Sivieri et al. showed with an in vitro study that with flow rates of 1e6 L/min and an open mouth, the distending pressure does not exceed 2 cmH₂O. In contrast in the same model

with the mouth closed, the pressure rises up to 10 cm H₂O [24]. With these pressure peaks the patient could be at risk of severe pressure dependent complications. Therefore, concerns about the wide spread use of HFNC as a potentially less invasive form of oxygen supply have been raised [25, 26].

Conclusion

HFNC is an effective and safe primary mode of respiratory support in children with respiratory distress due to various causes. Children who succeed on HFNC show favourable response within first few hours and response is sustained over the next few days.

References

1. C. Sreenan, R.P. Lemke, A. Hudson-Mason, H. Osiovich, High-flow nasal cannulae in the management of apnea of prematurity: a comparison with conventional nasal continuous positive airway pressure, *Pediatrics*. 2001; 107:1081e1083.
2. C. Dani, S. Pratesi, C. Migliori, G. Bertini, High flow nasal cannula therapy as respiratory support in the preterm infant, *Pediatr. Pulmonol*. 2009;44: 629e634,
3. F. Baudin, S. Gagnon, B. Crulli, F. Proulx, P. Jouvet, G. Emeriaud, Modalities and complications associated with the use of high-flow nasal cannula: experience in a pediatric ICU, *Respir. Care*. 2016;61; 1305e1310
4. Zhao H, Wang H, Sun F, Lyu S, An Y. High-flow nasal cannula oxygen therapy is superior to conventional oxygen therapy but not to noninvasive mechanical ventilation on intubation rate: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Crit Care*. 2017; 21:184.
5. Mikalsen IB, Davis P, Øymar K. High flow nasal cannula in children: a literature review. *Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med*. 2016; 24:93.
6. Mile'si C, Boubal M, Jacquot A, Baleine J, Durand S, Odena MP, et al. High-flow nasal cannula: recommendations for daily practice in pediatrics. *Ann Intensive Care*. 2014; 4:29.
7. Hutchings FA, Hilliard TN, Davis PJ. Heated humidified high flow nasal cannula therapy in children. *Arch Dis Child*. 2015;100:571–5.
8. Mile'si C, Baleine J, Matecki S, Durand S, Combes C, Novais ARB, et al. Is treatment with a high flow nasal cannula effective in acute viral bronchiolitis? A physiologic study. *Intensive Care Med*. 2013; 39:1088–94.
9. Hough JL, Pham TMT, Schibler A. Physiologic effect of high-flow nasal cannula in infants with bronchiolitis. *Pediatr Crit Care Med*. 2014; 15: e214–9.
10. Dysart K, Miller TL, Wolfson MR, Shaffer TH. Research in high flow therapy: mechanisms of action. *Respir Med*. 2009;103:1400–5.
11. Maggiore SM, Idone FA, Vaschetto R, Festa R, Cataldo A, Antonicelli F, et al. Nasal high-flow versus Venturi mask oxygen therapy after extubation: effects of oxygenation, comfort and clinical outcome. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 2014; 190:282–8.
12. M. Frizzola, T.L. Miller, M.E. Rodriguez, Y. Zhu, J. Rojas, A. Heseck, A. Stump, T.H. Shaffer, K. Dysart, High-flow nasal cannula: impact on oxygenation and ventilation in an acute lung injury model, *Pediatr. Pulmonol*. 2011;46: 67e74.
13. S. Mayfield, F. Bogossian, L. O'Malley, A. Schibler, High-flow nasal cannula oxygen therapy for infants with bronchiolitis: pilot study, *J. Paediatr. Child. Health*. 2014;50: 373e 378
14. A.L. Lampland, B. Plumm, P.A. Meyers, C.T. Worwa, M.C. Mammel, Observational study of humidified high-flow nasal cannula compared with

- nasal continuous positive airway pressure, *J. Pediatr.* 2009; 154: 177e182,
15. T.A. Volsko, K. Fedor, J. Amadei, R.L. Chatburn, High flow through a nasal cannula and CPAP effect in a simulated infant model, *Respir. Care.* 2011; 56: 1893e1900,
 16. G.Y. Chang, C.A. Cox, T.H. Shaffer, Nasal cannula, CPAP, and high-flow nasal cannula: effect of flow on temperature, humidity, pressure, and resistance, *Biomed. Instrum. Technol.* 2011; 45: 69e74,
 17. Pham TMT, O'Malley L, Mayfield S, Martin S, Schibler A. The effect of high flow nasal cannula therapy on the work of breathing in infants with bronchiolitis. *PediatrPulmonol.* 2015; 50:713–20.
 18. Coletti KD, Bagdure DN, Walker LK, Remy KE, Custer JW. High-flow nasal cannula utilization in pediatric critical care. *Respiratory care.* 2017 Aug 1;62 (8):1023-9.
 19. Crulli B, Loron G, Nishisaki A, Harrington K, Essouri S, Emeriaud G. Safety of paediatric tracheal intubation after non-invasive ventilation failure. *Pediatric Pulmonology.* 2016 Feb; 51 (2):165-72.
 20. Ramnarayan P, Schibler A. Glass half empty or half full? The story of high-flow nasal cannula therapy in critically ill children. *Intensive care medicine.* 2017 Feb;43(2):246-9.
 21. Porhomayon J, El-Solh AA, Pourafkari L, Jaoude P, Nader ND. Applications of nasal high-flow oxygen therapy in critically ill adult patients. *Lung.* 2016 Oct;194(5):705-14.
 22. Ritchie JE, Williams AB, Gerard C, Hockey H. Evaluation of a humidified nasal high-flow oxygen system, using oxygraphy, capnography and measurement of upper airway pressures. *Anaesthesia and intensive care.* 2011 Nov;39(6):1103-10.
 23. Hasan RA, Habib RH. Effects of flow rate and airleak at the nares and mouth opening on positive distending pressure delivery using commercially available high-flow nasal cannula systems: a lung model study. *Pediatric Critical Care Medicine.* 2011 Jan 1;12 (1): e29-33.
 24. Sivieri EM, Gerdes JS, Abbasi S. Effect of HFNC flow rate, cannula size, and nares diameter on generated airway pressures: an in vitro study. *Pediatric pulmonology.* 2013 May; 48 (5):506-14.
 25. Finer NN, Mannino FL. High-flow nasal cannula: a kinder, gentler CPAP? *The Journal of pediatrics.* 2009 Feb 1; 154(2):160-2.
 26. Pyar K. P., Su K. K., Wunna K., Aung Z. N. H., Maung N. L., Kyaw A. P., Hlaing S. W., Tun T. H., Htun S. M., Aung N. M., Than A. M., Mon M. K., Min W., Myint T. T., Ya K. Z., Win T., Shan M. A., Thu S. P., Aung Y. L., Aung Z. P., Kyaw M. T., Maung K. T., & Aung, H. L. Initial presenting symptoms and severity of SARS-CoV-2 Wild type, the Delta variant and the Omicron variant infected cases in early fourth wave of epidemics in Myanmar. *Journal of Medical Research and Health Sciences.* 2022; 5(1): 1765–1769.